

The FF Heuristic for Lifted Classical Planning: Technical Appendix

Augusto B. Corrêa¹, Florian Pommerening¹, Malte Helmert¹, Guillem Francès²

¹University of Basel, Switzerland

²Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain

{augusto.blaascorrea,florian.pommerening,malte.helmert}@unibas.ch
guillem.frances@upf.edu

Table 1 below is an extension of Table 2 in the paper “*The FF Heuristic for Lifted Classical Planning*” (Corrêa et al. 2022). It contains the coverage per-domain for both benchmark sets.

References

Corrêa, A. B.; Pommerening, F.; Helmert, M.; and Francès, G. 2022. The FF Heuristic for Lifted Classical Planning. In Honavar, V.; and Spaan, M., eds., *Proceedings of the Thirty-Sixth AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI 2022)*. AAAI Press.

Coverage	Datalog-Based Heuristics						Other Lifted Methods			Fast Downward	
	Eager			Lazy + PO			Eager			Eager	Lazy + PO
	h^{add}	h^{FF}	h^{R-FF}	h^{add}	h^{FF}	h^{R-FF}	h^{gc}	$h^{gc, ur-d}$	$h^{gc, ur}$	h^{FF}	h^{FF}
airport (50)	25	28	31	27	26	31	26	21	22	36	37
barman-sat14 (20)	0	0	0	0	20	18	0	0	0	11	12
blocks (35)	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
childsnack-sat14 (20)	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	1	9
depot (22)	9	15	8	17	20	21	14	11	11	17	18
driverlog (20)	15	16	17	14	14	14	19	14	14	18	20
freecell (80)	76	77	76	76	76	77	30	44	43	79	80
grid (5)	2	4	3	4	5	5	3	0	0	4	4
gripper (20)	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
logistics00 (28)	28	28	28	28	28	28	28	25	25	28	28
logistics98 (35)	16	20	19	24	32	32	5	5	5	29	33
miconic (150)	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	145	150	150
movie (30)	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
mystery (30)	18	16	16	17	17	17	15	3	3	17	18
nomystery-sat11 (20)	1	3	3	6	7	7	5	1	2	10	9
openstacks (30)	18	26	19	21	28	17	8	29	29	29	30
parking-sat11 (20)	13	20	18	20	20	20	0	0	0	20	20
parking-sat14 (20)	2	20	11	15	20	18	0	0	0	14	16
pipesworld-notankage (50)	23	28	24	37	39	38	35	15	14	31	42
pipesworld-tankage (50)	12	13	12	18	25	25	21	9	9	23	41
psr-small (50)	42	47	47	50	50	50	48	47	47	50	50
rovers (40)	15	18	19	39	40	40	18	28	29	26	40
satellite (36)	27	22	22	35	34	34	13	19	16	28	36
thoughtful-sat14 (20)	7	14	17	12	11	16	5	5	5	8	11
tpp (30)	15	15	15	28	30	30	12	13	13	23	30
trucks (30)	8	9	8	7	8	8	5	7	7	15	19
visitall-sat11 (20)	2	8	9	2	11	11	20	20	20	3	4
visitall-sat14 (20)	0	0	0	0	4	4	12	11	12	0	0
zenotravel (20)	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	13	13	20	20
IPC Sum (1001)	629	702	677	759	820	816	597	575	569	775	862
blocksworld-large (40)	1	4	0	6	9	4	4	7	7	4	12
childsnacks-large (144)	34	27	30	82	73	69	26	98	65	51	115
genome-edit-distance (312)	185	294	225	289	311	310	312	312	312	312	312
logistics-large (40)	8	9	9	40	40	40	20	0	0	30	32
organic-synthesis (56)	47	48	48	49	48	49	48	47	47	20	20
pipesworld-tankage-nosplit (50)	22	23	25	28	32	32	22	10	12	15	19
rovers-large (40)	11	36	36	40	40	40	1	16	14	11	13
visitall-multidimensional (180)	118	101	104	143	143	143	65	151	102	72	72
HTG Sum (862)	426	542	477	677	696	687	498	641	559	515	595
Total Sum (1863)	1055	1244	1154	1436	1516	1503	1095	1216	1128	1290	1457

Table 1: Coverage per-domain for all tested methods over both benchmark sets. Best results shown in bold typeface.